

THE DISCUSSION OF TRADITIONAL AND INTERNET COURSES

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***Abstract** Scholars have argued about the best educational method for decades. Some contend that online learning is better than conventional face-to-face learning, while others counter that it is ineffective. Others claim that the hybrid mode, which combines online learning with in-person lectures, is the most popular and effective way to provide knowledge to students. However, the attitudes of students about online learning vs conventional face-to-face learning have mainly been disregarded. This research aims to fill this gap in the literature by examining how minority students see online learning in comparison to traditional face-to-face forms of higher education.*

***Keywords:** traditional courses, online courses, student participation, Course delivery preferences.*

Introduction

People now have additional options for accessing possibilities for education that can change their lives because to the widespread availability of personal computers. Technology innovation has largely benefited the sector of education. Universities have been developing these technologies to extend the accessibility of classes via online and distant learning, where a student may participate in a class via a computer without setting foot on a typical campus environment.

Since the introduction of the online format, internet courses have gained popularity as more students choose this adaptable type of education. Online learning

is thus best understood as one of many outcomes of continuing technological advancement, which in recent decades began to pick up speed exponentially (Bailey 28).

Creation of online courses

The public Internet's introduction in the early 1990s made it feasible to create and deliver online courses. During this time, a few higher education institutions used the Internet as a teaching tool, although the earliest iterations of online education generally only offered textual content in digital form (Allen 21).

It is crucial to think carefully about how online courses should be created since it has an impact on their efficacy (Bailey 29). The National Center for Educational Statistics stated in 2000 that "a total of 1.6 million students, comprising 91% of public four-year colleges and about 50% of all private institutions, were now offering distance education programs provided via an online environment." (Bernard et al. 391).

A critique of traditional courses and online courses

Students enroll in classes for a variety of reasons, especially given how quickly the educational landscape is evolving. The students are aware that they might be able to complete their degrees outside of the typical on-campus teaching environments. The beauty of online learning, as stated by Clark-Ibanez and Scott, is that distance may be bridged through many interactive ways via the internet as opposed to through the static medium of a paper or a video distance education course.

For these reasons, students frequently choose for the online learning opportunities provided by several colleges, which are intended to enable them to pursue a degree while causing the least amount of disruption to their daily life.

People have more reasons to think about taking academic courses online because to the exponential advancement of digital technologies. The notion of distant learning has essentially stopped being exclusively connected with the

medium of traditional correspondence, i.e., direct connection between the student and the educator, as a result of the development of the internet.

As a result of the internet's ability to successfully erase the lengthy time lag in the process of students and educators talking with one another, people may currently enroll in schools and universities that are situated at the opposite ends of the planet. Due to this change, many sociologists now argue that traditional face-to-face schooling itself has become conceptually out of date (Erichsen and Bolliger 314).

Erichsen and Bolliger claim that dealing with information and communication technologies (ICT) is unavoidable for universities in the network society, both for research and instruction. Some even predict that colleges will transition to virtual learning environments (317). Surprisingly, unlike traditional college courses, online courses encourage less dependency on the lecturer, making them amenable to an integrated learning process (Carr par. 3).

Empirical analysis

According to the "discursively-interactive" learning theory, the methods used today to teach students in web-based formats are superior to those used in conventional college courses. According to the discursively-interactive paradigm, learner-educator contact should be proactive and kept within the parameters of the lesson.

Internet courses, in contrast to traditional courses, are more adaptable. In fact, "the dramatic changes taking place in online courses are focused on this fundamental meditational function of speech in learning" (Ramage, Bean, and Johnson 43). The expectation for online learning is that users would constantly be exposed to completely new discourses linked to education.

These discourses, which include active teacher-learner contact, assignments, and course material, allow online students to actively and critically engage with the content they have learned that is pertinent to their professional jobs (Clark-Ibanez and Scott 38).

Extrinsic and intrinsic motivational ideas have been classified in education. The proponents of an extrinsic method of student motivation contend that the motivating rewards offered by teachers must inevitably fall well within the purview of the course material. The proponents of an intrinsic method, on the other hand, say that students should be given psychologically appropriate incentives to continue their studies so they may remain fully dedicated to them.

The assumption made when motivation is used in the context of web-based learning is that many online students are less committed to their studies since their lecturers are not giving them significant 'external' educational incentives. However, it is unfair to dismiss online courses on the basis of motivation given that the idea of externally enforced educational discipline has never been a fundamental feature of online learning.

Everyone "is seen as having an inherent motivational system and a regulatory system that, by its "feedback," keeps the organism "on the beam" of satisfying his motivational needs," it is significant to note.

However, the fact that online learning eliminates geographical restrictions and offers educational chances for those who are already working is not the only reason why it is becoming more and more popular with people. The fundamental tenets of individual-centered education and the creation of settings that encourage learners to question dominant ideas are fully congruent with online learning (Ramage, Bean, and Johnson 35).

Flexibility: Because of the superior qualities of a web-based educational medium, both students and teachers have the chance to significantly improve the efficiency of their daily routines.

Technological friendliness: Students who are exposed to the online learning format are encouraged to work toward acquiring a fundamental understanding of information technology (Ramage, Bean, and Johnson 37).

Therefore, there are solid grounds for assuming that online students, as opposed to those who complete traditional college courses, will be better prepared

for the reality of post-industrial existence. Traditional students will only be able to understand the material if the professor is physically there. Since the world is rapidly embracing technology, online learners have better possibilities of integrating than conventional ones (Ramage, Bean, and Johnson 39).

Affordability: Online education not only makes it possible for students to pursue the academic degrees of their choosing regardless of where they live, but it is also more economical than taking regular college courses. The prices of acquiring an academic degree online may be defined as more affordable and flexible when compared to the costs of doing so in a typical classroom setting (Bernard et al. 392).

Internet courses, in contrast to conventional college courses, have set fees for each academic year. Since online courses don't need any tangible materials, once payment for an academic year is printed, there are no further adjustments possible. Since there are no costs associated with lodging, meals, transportation, or manual labor because everything is electronic, the affordability factor also applies.

Arguments in favor of conventional education over online education

Allen claims that a statistics course's online element has a 43 percent attrition rate compared to its conventional format counterpart's 13%. The attrition rate for a management marketing course was 24 percent for the online version against a rate of 9 percent for the traditional format (74).

It has been explored from a variety of angles, all of which may be broadly characterized according to how they promote a "academic" understanding of the nature of online student attrition. The first viewpoint's proponents contend that the fact that online learning is an inherently inconsistent format is the real cause of online students' manifestly insufficient level of academic dedication (Bailey 42).

The fact that online learning assumes the absence of teachers who are physically present is another aspect that might potentially reduce the degree of academic excitement on the side of online students. After all, such a presence has long since established itself as an essential component of a learning environment. The fact that the online learning format makes it more difficult for students to retain

the offered web-based knowledge is a third aspect that is frequently thought to add to the focus of educational issues experienced by online students.

Conclusion

It is clear from the explanation above that online courses are superior to conventional college courses in quality and efficacy. The online courses are more cost-effective, flexible with students' schedules, encourage proactive learner-educator engagement, and are in line with the current technology innovation in both the learning environment and the workplace.

Additionally, online courses enable students to achieve academic credentials without needing to be physically present throughout the learning process. Because online courses are adaptable, they lessen authoritarianism and linearity in the learning process, especially in settings where the teacher finds it difficult to connect socially with the students. However, since there is no face-to-face interaction between the students and the instructors, online courses are rigorous and may restrict a learner's social abilities. Actually, current online learning practices are still undergoing a qualitative transition, which will eventually make online courses even more effective and efficient than those offered in traditional colleges.

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